

ANALYTIC EXPRESSION FOR THE DEFORMATION AND BALLISTIC LIMIT OF FABRICS

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ABSTRACT: Fabrics are important components in modern light armors. Fabrics stop low velocity handgun rounds and fragments directly, and are used as backing material in armors to stop higher velocity rounds. This paper presents a constitutive model for an anisotropic fabric sheet based on elastic deformation of the fibers. Equations of motion for the fabric are then derived. The specific case of a centerpoint deflection of the fabric sheet is solved, giving a final shape for the statically deformed fabric. This leads to a force vs. deflection curve that, combined with inertial terms and an expression for transverse wave speed in the fabric, leads to an explicit equation for ballistic limit. This equation is shown to agree extremely well with data for Kevlar. The situation of fabrics impregnated with resin is also discussed.

KEYWORDS: Impact and dynamic response, Fabric deflection, Fabric anisotropy, Ballistic limit, Textiles

FABRICS

Fabrics are an extremely important element of body armors. Understanding fabrics analytically is difficult since fabric sheets are anisotropic and there is crimping and slippage between fibers. This paper outlines an analytical model that has been developed for the ballistic response of a fabric [1]. It then goes on to examine an extension of the ideas to composite panels [2]. The equations of motion for a plain-woven fabric sheet assuming both out-of-plane and in-plane motion, are derived where anisotropy is included. Once the constitutive model for the fabric is developed, an approximate solution for a static deflection problem is found. The constitutive model can be viewed as a continuum version of the numerical methods that have been employed to model fabrics over the past few decades [3]. The approximate solution is shown to match full numerical solutions of the same problem very well. Then the equation for force versus deflection is presented. The propagation velocity for transverse waves in the fabric is discussed. These various pieces are then combined to model impact directly onto fabrics. An explicit expression for calculating the ballistic limit for fabric sheets is presented. It is compared to data and gives extremely good results. Model predictions are compared with experimental data, and it is shown that agreement is excellent.

Fabric Constitutive Equations

The fabric will be modeled as an extended system of springs, connected at each corner (Fig. 1). The stresses in the presentation below are the Piola-Kirchhoff stresses since the derivations are with respect to the reference configuration. The strain in the spring connecting the points ij and $ij+1$ will be referred to as the x strain and is equal to:

$$\varepsilon_x = \frac{\sqrt{(\Delta x)^2 + (\Delta y)^2 + (\Delta z)^2}}{\Delta x_o} - 1 \quad (1)$$

where Δx_0 is the original length of the spring. The strain that will be used in this paper is the large deformation strain E where $E = \frac{1}{2}(F^T F - 1)$ and F is the deformation gradient $F_{ij} = \delta_{ij} + \partial u_i / \partial x_j$. For example, in the limit as $\Delta x_0 \rightarrow 0$, $\varepsilon_x = E_{11}$. An elastic stress-strain relation is assumed of the form

$$\sigma_{11} = EE_{11} \quad (2)$$

Viewing the fabric strand as a linear elastic spring, the energy stored in the deformation of the spring is:

$$P.E. = \int EE_{11} dE_{11} = \frac{E}{2} E_{11}^2 \quad (3)$$

The expression for a potential energy density for the fabric with strands running in both the x direction and y direction is:

$$e = \frac{E}{2} (E_{11}^2 + E_{22}^2) \quad (4)$$

This potential applies to an ideal fabric with a plain weave and no slippage between fibers. The Piola-Kirchhoff stress S is obtained from the energy density, Eq. (4), through differentiation with respect to the components of the deformation gradient F [4]:

$$S_{ij} = \frac{\partial e}{\partial F_{ij}} \quad (5)$$

For example, for the 11 component of the stress, the result is

$$S_{11} = E \left(E_{11} \frac{\partial E_{11}}{\partial F_{11}} + E_{22} \frac{\partial E_{22}}{\partial F_{11}} \right) = EE_{11} F_{11} \quad (6)$$

It is straight show that the complete

Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor is

$$S = E \begin{pmatrix} E_{11} F_{11} & E_{22} F_{12} & 0 \\ E_{11} F_{21} & E_{22} F_{22} & 0 \\ E_{11} F_{31} & E_{22} F_{32} & 0 \end{pmatrix} = EF \begin{pmatrix} E_{11} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & E_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} = EF\Lambda \quad (7)$$

where Λ is defined by the equation. The Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor is not symmetric.

Figure 1. Fabric model: an extended set of connected springs.

Once the stresses have been explicitly found, it is possible to determine the equations of motion for the fabric with respect to the initial coordinates. They are

$$\frac{\tilde{\rho}}{\tilde{T}} \frac{d^2 u_i}{dt^2} = \frac{\partial S_{ij}}{\partial x_j} \quad (8)$$

where $\tilde{\rho}$ is the areal density and \tilde{T} is the thickness of the fabric sheet (actually, \tilde{T} is the areal density of the fabric $\tilde{\rho}$ divided by the density of the fibers ρ_{fiber} – the physical thickness obtained by measurement may be larger due to empty regions in the weave and the way the strands cross and lay on each other).

Approximate Static Deflection Solution

The approximate analytical solution for static deflection has the features seen in tests with fabrics – a roughly pyramidal shape with curvature along the principal axes [5,6]. A first step in finding the approximate analytical solution is solving the problem where all the motion is out-of-plane; that is, where $u_x = u_y = 0$. This motion is sometimes referred to as anti-plane shear. The solution will be for static deformation of a single fabric sheet under loading conditions similar to those experienced in a ballistic event and similar to those seen in static tests. The solution to the strictly out-of-plane problem will then be used to find an approximate solution to the complete problem.

Assuming that the motion is strictly out-of-plane says F , Λ and the stress are

$$F = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial y} & 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ F_{31} & F_{32} & 1 \end{pmatrix}; \quad \Lambda = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} F_{31}^2 & & \\ & F_{32}^2 & \\ & & 0 \end{pmatrix}; \quad S = \frac{E}{2} \begin{pmatrix} \left(\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial x}\right)^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \left(\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial y}\right)^2 & 0 \\ \left(\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial x}\right)^3 & \left(\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial y}\right)^3 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

The equation of motion in the z direction is

$$\frac{\tilde{\rho}}{\tilde{T}} \frac{d^2 u_z}{dt^2} = \frac{E}{2} \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial x} \right)^3 + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial y} \right)^3 \right\} \quad (10)$$

For the static case, with the boundary held fixed and the fabric indented at the center, Eq. (10) can be solved explicitly. On the boundary it is assumed that $u_z(R,0) = 0$ and $u_z(0,R) = 0$. Part of the problem is finding the boundary curve that connects $(R,0)$ and $(0,R)$ on which $u_z(x,y) = 0$. The deformed height at the center is denoted $h = u_z(0,0)$. Considering only the first quadrant introduces boundary conditions along the x - and y -axis:

$$\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial x} = 0 \quad \text{for } x = 0; \quad \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial y} = 0 \quad \text{for } y = 0; \quad (11)$$

$u_z = 0$ along a plane curve to be determined

Since some type of symmetry is expected in the problem, an assumed form of solution is introduced. The form of r below is quite general:

$$u_z(x,y) = u(r), \quad r = x^\lambda + y^\lambda \quad (12)$$

For the static problem, Eq. (10) reduces to

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial x} \right)^3 + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial y} \right)^3 = 3\lambda^3 (u')^2 \left\{ x^{3\lambda-4} ((\lambda-1)u' + \lambda x^\lambda u'') + y^{3\lambda-4} ((\lambda-1)u' + \lambda y^\lambda u'') \right\} = 0 \quad (13)$$

where prime denotes differentiation with respect to r . The expression $3\lambda - 4$ suggests $\lambda = 4/3$. This leads to the term in brackets equaling

$$\frac{2}{3}u' + \frac{4}{3}ru'' = 0 \quad (14)$$

This ordinary differential equation has a solution

$$u(r) = c_1 \sqrt{r} + c_2 \quad (15)$$

where c_1 and c_2 are arbitrary constants, and are found based on the boundary conditions.

This gives the solution to the out-of-plane fabric deformation problem. The boundary curve on which the deflection is zero is $r = R^{4/3}$. The solution is

$$u_z(x, y) = h \left\{ 1 - \sqrt{(x/R)^{4/3} + (y/R)^{4/3}} \right\} \quad (16)$$

The solution satisfies the boundary conditions on the axes, Eq. (11). It might be thought that the linear $u_z = a + bx + cy$ (a straight-sided pyramid) also satisfies the Eq. (10). However, it does not satisfy the boundary conditions, Eq. (11), and is therefore not a solution to the center-indented problem.

To obtain an in-plane displacement, the equation of motion for the in-plane motion in the x -direction is written, Eq. (8):

$$\frac{\tilde{\rho}}{\tilde{T}} \frac{d^2 u_x}{dt^2} = E \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial x} (F_{11} E_{11}) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} (F_{12} E_{22}) \right\} \quad (17)$$

This case is more tedious to work out, but it can be shown to yield [2]

$$u_x(x, y) = -\frac{2}{3} \frac{h^2}{R} \left\{ 1 - (y/R)^{4/3} \right\}^{1/4} \left\{ \left(1 - (y/R)^{2/3} \right) \left[1 - \frac{x/R}{\left\{ 1 - (y/R)^{4/3} \right\}^{3/4}} \right] + \sqrt{(x/R)^{4/3} + (y/R)^{4/3} - 1} \right\} \quad (18)$$

By symmetry, the u_y solution is $u_y(x, y) = u_x(y, x)$. Examples of the solution are given in Figs. 2 and 3. Figure 2 shows the view from above the fabric sheet, showing the contours on which the z displacement is constant. These curves are given by:

$$x^{4/3} + y^{4/3} = \text{constant} \quad (19)$$

The outer curve is the boundary curve, one of the original unknowns, on which the $u_z(x, y) = 0$. The dot-dash lines are straight lines to give a better feel for the curvature in the solution. Figure 3 shows the solution along the x -axis compared to a full transient numerical solution (similar to [7]). Along the axis the x displacement is (from Eq. 18)

$$u_x(x, 0) = \frac{2}{3} \frac{h^2}{R} \left\{ \frac{x}{R} - \left(\frac{x}{R} \right)^{2/3} \right\} \quad (20)$$

The curvature is similar to that seen in [5]. Agreement between the two solutions is excellent. Again, the straight lines (dotted) are for comparison. The general pyramid shape seen in tests is evident in these solutions.

The ε_x for the analytic solution derived above can be calculated using Eqs. (16) and (18), and along the x -axis it reduces to

$$\varepsilon_x \approx \frac{2}{9} \left(\frac{h}{R} \right)^2 \left\{ \left(\frac{R}{x} \right)^{2/3} - 2 \left(\frac{R}{x} \right)^{1/3} + 3 \right\} \quad (21)$$

Figure 2. Curves of constant z -deflection. Dot-dashed lines are straight lines to compare solution curvature against.

Figure 3. Analytic solution along x -axis compared to full numerical solution.

Equation (21) explains why fabrics break at a time later than at impact. Tests show that h/R is often constant during an impact event [6]. As the impact event proceeds, the radius R expands. However x is fixed since it is the radius of the projectile. Thus, as the impact progresses, x/R decreases, and the strains slowly increase until the fiber failure strain is reached.

Force vs. Deflection

A force versus deflection curve identifies how a clamped piece of fabric resists a center indentation. If the loading surface indenting the fabric is taken to be that described by the curve $x^{4/3} + y^{4/3} = \tilde{R}^{4/3}$, where $\tilde{R} < R$, then the force required to deflect the fabric to a height h along the centerline is given by

$$F_z = \int_{\partial A} E\tilde{T} \{ \varepsilon_x \sin(\theta_x) + \varepsilon_y \sin(\theta_y) \} dl \quad (22)$$

where ∂A is the boundary of the region. Inserting Eqs. (16) and (18) into Eq. (22) and evaluation of the integral shows an \tilde{R} dependence, and an approximate evaluation gives

$$F_z = -\frac{8}{9} \frac{h^3}{R^2} E\tilde{T} \quad (23)$$

The force depends on the cube of the deflection. Such cubic behavior is also seen in shell and membrane theories [8,9].

Transverse Wave Speed in the Fabric

Early work to determine a transverse wave speed in the fabric was based on reasoning that over time has been brought into question. In fact, the question of the transverse wave speed in a fabric sheet is listed as one of the important open problems in ballistics in [10]. However, early work, where $c_f = \sqrt{E/\rho_{fiber}}$ is the bar wave speed in the fiber, gave

$$\frac{h}{R} = \frac{Vt}{ct} = \sqrt{\frac{V}{c_f}} \quad \text{or} \quad c = \sqrt{c_f V} \quad (24)$$

This form has the important mathematical property that it allows an explicit ballistic limit curve due to the fact that the transverse wave speed is proportional to the square root of V . Thus, it will be used here, with the caveats noted above. For more discussion of the transverse wave speed see [2,10]. Also compare with the explicitly calculable transverse wave speed for a single fiber (e.g., [9,11,12]).

Fabric Ballistic Limit

The final step in determining the ballistic limit is to combine the force versus deflection curve and the region of affected fabric with a momentum balance. The equation of motion for a projectile impacting a fabric is given by Eq. (23):

$$(m_p + m_f) \frac{dv}{dt} = F_z = -\frac{8}{9} \left(\frac{h}{R} \right)^2 E \tilde{T} h \quad (25)$$

where m_p is the mass of the projectile, m_f is the mass of the fabric directly involved in the region of the projectile, and v is the projectile velocity. If the shape of the deformed fabric remains self-similar as deflection increases - behavior clearly seen in photographs of impact on fabrics [6] - then h/R is constant. Use of $dv/dt = vdv/dh$ leads to

$$v^2 - V^2 = -\frac{8}{9} \left(\frac{h}{R} \right)^4 c_f^2 \frac{\tilde{\rho}}{m_p + m_f} R^2 \quad (26)$$

Since the fabric motion just comes to rest at the ballistic limit, Eq. (26) becomes:

$$V_{bl}^2 = \frac{8}{9} \left(\frac{h}{R} \right)^4 c_f^2 \frac{\tilde{\rho}}{m_p + m_f} R_{bl}^2 \quad (27)$$

where R_{bl} is the radial extent of the fabric involved in the impact as it comes to rest at the ballistic limit velocity. Equations (24) and (27) allow a calculation of R_{bl} :

$$\frac{R_{bl}}{R_p} = \sqrt{\frac{9(m_p + m_f)}{8\tilde{\rho}R_p^2}} = \sqrt{\frac{9\pi}{8} \left(\frac{1}{X} + \beta \right)} \quad (28)$$

here R_p is the radius of the projectile, assumed to be a right circular cylinder impacting on end, and X is the areal density of the fabric times the presented area of the projectile divided by the mass of the projectile

$$X = \frac{\tilde{\rho}\pi R_p^2}{m_p} \quad (29)$$

With this definition, $m_f = \beta X m_p$. X has been found by Phil Cunniff to be an important variable in scaling ballistic response of fabrics [13]. β is the area multiplier of the fabric carried along by the projectile, and it will be taken to be $\beta = (1.6)^2 = 2.56$, i.e., an additional 60% projectile radius of fabric beyond the presented area of the projectile is carried along directly by the projectile ($m_f = \beta\pi R_p^2 \tilde{\rho}$).

The initial momentum transfer bringing this amount of fabric up to speed is included in the ballistic limit expression:

$$V(0) = \frac{m_p}{m_p + m_f} V_{\text{impact}} \quad (30)$$

Assuming the fabric breaks at a strain ε_f , the ballistic limit equation for the fabric is obtained through the strain equation from the explicit static solution, Eq. (21), and from the h/R expression, Eq. (24):

$$V_{bl} = \frac{9}{2}(1 + \beta X)c_f \varepsilon_f \left\{ \left(\frac{R_{bl}}{R_p} \right)^{2/3} - 2 \left(\frac{R_{bl}}{R_p} \right)^{1/3} + 3 \right\}^{-1} \quad (31)$$

Figure 4 compares the analytic curve with V_{50} data for Kevlar® KM2 (850 denier yarns), with $c_f = 7154$ m/s and $\varepsilon_f = 3.8\%$. This data is for a wide range of projectile sizes, from 2 to 64 grain (0.25 to 4.15 g), and for 12 to 44 sheets of fabric (for the particular fabric used, 44 sheets has $\tilde{\rho} = 1.0$ g/cm²). The agreement is excellent. Cunniff has shown that V_{50} data for many fabrics falls on an experimental “universal” scaled data curve [13].

Equation (28) deserves discussion, for it is quite remarkable. It predicts that the radius R_{bl} of fabric material involved in the deformation at the ballistic limit—i.e., when the projectile comes to rest just as the strain in the fabric at the point of maximal strain (the fabric in contact with the outer radius of the projectile) reaches the fiber failure strain—does not depend on the fabric elastic properties. In particular, it depends only on the areal density of the fabric, the amount of fabric inertially involved, and the mass and face area of the projectile; it does not depend on failure strain or wave speed of the fiber. The deflection of the fabric h and the ballistic limit velocity do depend on the material properties of the fabric. Given two different fabrics of the same areal density, Eq. (28) predicts the same R_{bl} , though the ballistic limit velocities would differ, Eq. (31).

Figure 4. Analytical ballistic limit prediction compared with V_{50} data for Kevlar® KM2.

COMPOSITES

Composite panels made from fabrics and resin are also important components in modern light armors. Experimental work with panels made from fabrics and resin has indicated that for a few sheets of fabric, "dry is better," meaning that fabric sheets with no resin (hence dry) will outperform the equivalent areal density of a fabric/resin composite [13,14]. Simply put, for low relative areal densities of fabric, the loss in fabric material by adding resin in order to maintain the same areal density leads to a loss in performance of the armor system. However, as the relative areal density increases, the fabric/resin composite panel begins to show bending stiffness, and its performance increases. Experimentally it has been observed that the crossover in ballistic limit performance is in the region of $X=1/\beta$ (see comments below). However, as the number of fabric sheets increases, additional mechanisms are involved. There are five mechanisms that come into play as resin is added to fabric:

- 1) As noted above, removal of fibers when resin is added (to maintain the same areal density) tends to reduce the ballistic limit since (especially for thin sheets) the ballistic resistance is in the tensile strength of the fibers.
- 2) The increase in resin leads to a resistance to bending in the fabric/resin composite (as opposed to the dry fabric that only has tensile membrane stresses), thus increasing the panel's resistance to deformation and thus increasing the ballistic limit;
- 3) The newly acquired bending strength leads to an increase in the transverse wave speed, thus reducing the strain and increasing the ballistic limit;
- 4) The now harder panel deforms the projectile, leading to an increase in the presented area of the projectile and thus leading to an increase in the ballistic limit;
- 5) It is possible that for larger amounts of resin the harder panel will rigidly hold the fabric, allowing the fibers to be sheared by the projectile rather than failing in tension (their optimal failure mode), thus leading to a reduction in ballistic limit.

These mechanisms all have a role, but here the focus will be on the first two mechanisms, where it is possible to quantitatively estimate the magnitude of the effect. It can be shown that the reduction in fabric reduces the ballistic limit as $\sqrt{1-r}$, where r is the mass fraction of the resin, since the Young's modulus enters into the ballistic limit equation through a square root term (in c_f — see Eq. 31). Resistance to bending in beams and plates is proportional to the moment of inertia of the beam or plate, which for a constant cross section is proportional to the cube of the thickness. For the fabric with resin, the thickness of the plate will be assumed proportional to the areal density, and so it is possible to write heuristically the increase in stiffness of the plate in the form $E = E_f(1-r)(1 + \gamma(r)X^3)$ where γ is a function of r that is to be determined. Experimentally, the ballistic limit of the fabric with resin and the dry fabric often occurs in the vicinity of $X = 0.3$ to 0.5 , and so here it will be approximated by $X = 1/\beta = 0.39$. (This assumption is intriguing, since it says that the crossover in ballistic limit behavior occurs when $\beta A_p \tilde{\rho} = m_p$, i.e. that it occurs at the point where the mass of the fabric or fabric/resin panel inertially involved in the impact event equals the mass of the projectile.) These assumptions give $\gamma(r) = r\beta^3/(1-r)$ which gives as an expression for ballistic limit velocity (again, the adjustment comes through c_f in Eq. 31)

$$V_{bl}(X, r) = \sqrt{1-r + r(\beta X)^3} V_{bl}(X, 0) \quad (32)$$

Equation (31) and Eq. (32) applied to Eq. (31) are shown in Fig. 5 for 1000 denier Kevlar 29, $c_f = 7400$ m/s and $\epsilon_f = 3.25\%$ [13], and the composite panel is 18% resin ($r = 0.18$). The curves agree well with the data taken from [13]. The experimental degradation in ballistic limit velocity is greater than predicted for small X . Also shown is a curve with $r = 0.4$, to give an idea of the mass fraction required to match the small X ballistic limit data. Overall, the agreement is good.

SUMMARY

Ballistic fabrics are an important element of body armor systems. A constitutive model that takes into account the anisotropy in a sheet for a plain weave has been presented and an explicit approximate analytic solution has been found that agrees remarkably well with full numerical solutions. The analytic solution led to a force versus deflection curve for the fabric. All these elements were then combined to produce an analytic expression for the ballistic limit of fabrics. The analytical curves agree extremely well with data for a wide range of projectile weights and numbers of fabric sheets. The analytic expression for ballistic limit shows that to improve the ballistic performance of fabrics it is most important to increase the strain energy to failure of the fiber. For composites comprised of fabrics and resin, it has been shown that "dry is better" for relatively low areal densities of fabric because of the loss of fabric mass and thus tensile strength while adding resin and maintaining the same areal density. However, as the relative areal density increases, the composite fabric/resin panel begins to show bending stiffness, and the increase in deformation resistance due to bending strength soon compensates for the loss of fabric material, and in fact as the relative thickness of the composite panel increases, there is an increase in the ballistic limit of the fabric/resin system, as compared to the dry fabric for the same areal density. An equation to predict the ballistic limit curve of the fabric/resin composite panel given the ballistic limit curve of the dry fabric was produced. The analytic expression agrees well with experimental data.

Figure 5. Ballistic limit curves for dry Kevlar 29 fabric and Kevlar 29/resin composite panel; points are data from [13]; curves are from Eqs. (31) and (32).

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